

Toxic metabolites produced in the blood in asthma.

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This study describes for the first time toxic metabolic activity in the blood in the human autoimmune inflammatory disease asthma, those whose contribution to the asthmatic phenotype is not yet understood. Pathophysiologic activation of metabolic was evidenced by transcriptional induction of enzymes *OLAH* (oleoyl-ACP hydrolase), a gene functioning in fatty acid metabolism, *ASS1* (argininosuccinate synthase 1), *ARG1*, *GLUL*, and *TYR* (tyrosinase). Loss of T-bet expression in childhood asthma thus occurs in an altered metabolic environment. The combination of metabolites produced by activation of the enzymes described here is likely a requisite component for aggressive and sustained disease activity in humans with asthma.

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